

What about the management of lithiasis pancreatitis in Algeria

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ABSTRACT:

Acute pancreatitis is an inflammation of the pancreatic gland, with varying degrees of extension to neighboring organs and probable repercussions, depending on its severity, on the body's major vital functions. Its management is multi-disciplinary and involves several specialties, due to the multiplicity of its aetiologies on the one hand, and the variety of its clinical presentation on the other. Management also depends on the severity and stage of the disease, so initial management is almost common to all aetiologies, but is then necessarily adapted to the aetiology, since only etiological treatment can guarantee effective prevention of recurrence. A number of questions remain unanswered in the therapeutic management of acute pancreatitis, and deserve to be addressed in order to improve morbidity-mortality outcomes. Biliary pancreatitis remains the most frequent aetiology in Algeria, with the specific problem of the timing of etiological treatment, and that of exploration of the main bile duct. The use of antibiotics and the timing of reintroduction of enteral feeding, and the place of parenteral nutrition are all questions that are arousing interest, opening the way to interesting research topics.

Keywords: acute pancreatitis, cholecystectomy, antibiotic therapy, severity diagnosis.

INTRODUCTION:

Acute pancreatitis is a pathology at the crossroads of several specialties: gastroenterology, digestive and visceral surgery, intensive care and radiology, immunology and biochemistry laboratory specialties are all called upon to manage patients presenting with this pathology, but the role and timing of each specialist's intervention remains to be debated. The inclusion of epidemiology specialists on this panel of practitioners should improve visibility of the figures, since epidemiological data on acute pancreatitis are unsatisfactory, both in quantity and quality. Publications on acute pancreatitis in Algeria are few and far between, often based on retrospective studies with a low level of evidence [1]. The recommendations of learned societies for the management of the pathology remain without update since the Atlanta 2012 meeting, which opens the wide way to research studies in the field, but not only that since it results in a lack of homogeneity in the collection of data on acute pancreatitis and particularly on severe forms and their complications [1]. The incidence of acute pancreatitis is rising steadily in Europe, but in different ways in different countries [2]. average age of onset of acute pancreatitis worldwide is between 53 and 59 years; in Algeria, this age is slightly lower, at around 51years

[1]. There are many aetiologies for acute pancreatitis. In Europe, biliary aetiology is more likely to be found in individuals in their fifth decade, and alcohol consumption in those in their third and fourth decades. However, the two aetiologies are neck and neck overall [2]. In our country, biliary aetiology accounts for around 68.25% of cases, compared with only 07% for alcoholic aetiology [1]. The management of acute pancreatitis has made considerable progress since the organization of consensus meetings, which set out the main guidelines for the patient's progress. Morbidity and mortality are becoming increasingly acceptable, but still need to be improved, given that this is often a benign pathology.

Positive diagnosis of acute pancreatitis:

Since the recommendations of the Atlanta 2012 meeting, which developed the classification of acute pancreatitis, the diagnostic approach has become simpler and more effective. The definition of acute pancreatitis therefore requires the presence of 2 of the following 3 criteria to make the diagnosis of acute pancreatitis:

- Abdominal pain suggestive of pancreatitis;
- Serum lipase greater than 3 times the upper limit of normal;

- Imaging (CT or MRI) consistent with acute pancreatitis [3].

In the majority of cases (80%), the diagnosis is clinico-biological, with a clinical picture of classically intense and constant abdominal pain, epigastric, transfixing or radiating to the right or left hypochondrium, associated with nausea and/or vomiting. There is usually a marked contrast between the intensity of functional signs and the paucity of physical signs. Elevation of serum lipase above three times the norm. This lipase assay should be performed only once, as its repetition over time has no diagnostic or prognostic value [3].

The use of radiology for diagnostic purposes has been accepted since Atlanta 2012, the context may be justified by the patient's delayed consultation which may allow time for clinical signs to subside and lipasemia levels to normalize, or to rule out a differential diagnosis such as ulcer perforation or entero-mesenteric infarction.

If CT is used to diagnose acute pancreatitis, care must be without inject contrast if the patient is dehydrated, or has associated renal failure. On the contrary, it may conceal calcifications from underlying chronic pancreatitis, or a calculus embedded in the ampulla of Vater.

Magnetic resonance imaging currently offers the same performance as CT, with a lower radiation risk, and is less aggressive for the kidneys in this acute inflammatory context.

Radiological findings in favor of acute pancreatitis range from simple inflammatory infiltration of the pancreatic parenchyma, to parenchymal hemorrhagic necrosis and distant necrotic flows. Distant signs may also be detected, such as the classic left pleural effusion, or even less so, peritoneal ascites.

Prove the biliary origin of acute pancreatitis:

The *primum movens* of acute biliary pancreatitis, according to the ductal theory described by Eugene Opie, is the passage of a gallstone through the sphincter of Oddi, causing impaction and obstruction, often transient. This impaction generates intra-canal pancreatic hyperpressure, with possible reflux of bile into the canal of Wirsung, leading to enzyme activation and inflammation of the pancreatic parenchyma and its "autodigestion".

In Algeria, biliary aetiology remains the most frequent, accounting for 68.45% of all aetiologies [1] In Europe, the incidence of acute pancreatitis of biliary origin is increasing in the elderly [1,2]. The female gender is more affected, since biliary pathology is essentially a woman's disease, in contrast to alcoholic pancreatitis, which is predominantly male and associated with the abuse of alcoholic beverages.

Proof of the biliary aetiology is necessary to undertake a therapeutic strategy that will prevent recurrence. This strategy involves, but is not limited to, cholecystectomy, the timing and modalities of which

depend essentially on the severity of the acute pancreatitis.

Episodes of hepatic cholelithiasis that resolve spontaneously, or are calmed by medication, are sought in the history. If there is a history of uninvestigated acute pancreatitis, cholecystectomy does not rule out a biliary aetiology, since autochthonous lithiasis of lithogenic bile cannot be ruled out.

The timing of blood sampling is essential, as most abnormalities are transient. For example, a transient elevation of transaminases within the first 48 hours has a positive predictive value of 85% for the diagnosis of lithiasis migration, but has no diagnostic value beyond this time [4]. The Blamey score (1983) is a good element of biliary etiological orientation:

- Age over 50
- Female gender
- ALT greater than 2 times the normal level
- Alkaline phosphatase greater than 2.5 times the normal level
- Amylasemia greater than 13 times the normal level

The score is positive if three items are present, with a sensitivity of 60% and a specificity of 87%.

The abdominal x-ray should no longer be used in the assessment of AP. Often normal; it may show a sentinel small loop (air-filled satellite loop and/or duodenal ileus) or a more diffuse reflex ileus [5]. Its only value in the context of an acute abdominal pain syndrome is to rule out pneumoperitoneum, as a digestive perforation may simulate an AP picture.

Abdominal ultrasonography is the classic investigation for acute abdominal pain syndromes. In acute pancreatitis, it is of great value for etiological orientation, as it visualizes direct or indirect signs of biliary lithiasis (dilatation of the bile ducts). This examination may be hampered by gas in the acute phase, so it must be repeated if necessary.

Echo-endoscopy is the gold standard for proving biliary aetiology if transparietal ultrasonography fails to visualize biliary lithiasis; it even appears to be superior to MRI for stones smaller than 5 mm [6], although it may not be productive if performed early due to inflammatory phenomena. This examination, like MRI, makes it possible to avoid unnecessary ERCP by verifying the vacuity of the main bile duct. The availability and expertise of this examination is gaining ground in both public and private hospitals.

MRI is a highly valuable examination, enabling a complete review of biliopancreatic mapping, with good sensitivity for stones larger than 05 mm in diameter [5,6]. It is a non-invasive, non-irradiation examination, and is therefore useful in pregnant women. In addition to aetiology, MRI can establish a degree of local severity (necrosis) similar to CT [7].

Finally, CT does not have a good predictive value for the visualization of gallstones, although it remains the

examination of choice for morphological assessment of severity [8].

Finally, when faced with a confirmed positive diagnosis, the urgency is not to establish the etiological diagnosis, but rather to begin the therapeutic management that is initially common to all aetiologies. Progress has been made in the availability of aetiological diagnostics, particularly morphological, in Algeria, and efforts have been made by the private sector to support the public sector in this area.

Severity diagnosis of acute lithiasis pancreatitis:

This is a crucial stage in the management of acute lithiasis pancreatitis. The degree of severity is decisive for further management, particularly with regard to the timing of cholecystectomy. Several scores have been used to assess the severity of acute pancreatitis, the best known being the Ranson score.

Historically, a distinction was made between benign oedematous or oedemato-interstitial forms and severe necrotizing forms. Necrotizing APs are more likely to be accompanied by systemic and locoregional complications, with the risk of superinfection, and are therefore considered more risky and severe than oedematous AP.

The Atlanta Revised Classification (ARC) is the best-known and most widely accepted classification system. It classifies AP into mild (or mildly severe), moderately severe and severe subtypes:

Mild AP is characterized by the absence of organ failure and local or systemic complications:

Moderately severe AP is characterized by the presence of transient organ failure (< 48 h), and/or local or systemic complications without persistent organ failure. Severe AP is characterized by persistent (> 48 h) single and/or multiple organ failure [9]. The only score that meets the criteria defined by the ACR is the Systemic Inflammatory Response Syndrome (SIRS) score. SIRS is defined by the association of two or more of the following conditions:

- Temperature < 36°C or > 38°C ;
- Heart rate > 90/min ;
- Respiratory rate > 20/min or PaCO₂ < 32 mmHg ;
- Leukocytosis > 12,000/mm³, < 4,000/ m³ or presence of circulating immature forms (> 10% of cells).

Its presence on admission and, above all, its persistence for more than 48 hours predicts a severe evolution and an increased risk of mortality.

Radiological scores, in particular the CTSI, are a good way of assessing the degree of local inflammation, and are therefore much appreciated by surgeons for giving them an idea of the anatomical state prevailing before any surgical procedure.

With so many scores to choose from, we recommend using the SIRS as an easy, reproducible bioclinical score, but also because it is simple and inexpensive enough to meet the needs of the field in our country. The CTSI score is also useful for surgeons, so the combination of these scores seems logical. [10,11] Access to CT in Algeria is becoming increasingly easy, as it is being installed throughout the country in public and private facilities.

How and when to perform cholecystectomy:

Acute lithiasis pancreatitis is distinguished by the possibility of etiological treatment, which theoretically prevents recurrence. The timing of the operation used to be the subject of controversy among surgeons, who tended to postpone it because of the inflammatory phenomena in the bilio-pancreatic junction following the relapse. Since then, a number of studies have demonstrated the safety of early cholecystectomy in patients with non-severe acute pancreatitis [12,13,14]. Better still, early cholecystectomy avoids the complications associated with biliary lithiasis [12]. In the case of severe pancreatitis, the delay depends on the evolution of the pancreatitis and its local and general complications [15,16]. It should always be borne in mind that recurrence is possible, and so cholecystectomy should be performed as soon as the patient's situation allows.

The laparoscopic approach remains the first choice, with an acceptable conversion rate close to that observed in cholecystectomy for uncomplicated vesicular lithiasis [12,13]. Training in laparoscopic surgery in Algeria has progressed significantly, and the generation currently practising must be aware that this approach is the gold standard for this pathology. Conversion should not be seen as a failure, but rather as a logical response to a difficult surgical situation.

Place of ERCP in the management of acute lithiasis pancreatitis:

Early ERCP has no indication in benign biliary AP.

- ERCP is probably not indicated in severe biliary AP without angiocholitis.
- ERCP is probably indicated in cases of biliary PA associated with biliary obstruction (calculus lodged in the ampulla of Vater, or lithiasis of the main bile duct associated with acute pancreatitis), with a view to complete treatment of the biliary lithiasis.
- ERCP is indicated in cases of biliary AP associated with angiocholitis, in which case it should be performed as soon as possible, ideally within 24 hours.
- In conclusion, ERCP is indicated in cases of biliary AP associated with angiocholitis or biliary obstruction. Outside these indications, ERCP has shown no benefit and therefore has no place [17,18].

CONCLUSION:

Biliary lithiasis is the most frequent aetiology in the genesis of acute pancreatitis, and its management necessarily involves a proper assessment of severity, and a better methodology for labelling the biliary cause. Cholecystectomy remains the only effective etiological treatment, and one that avoids recurrence. The best approach to acute lithiasis pancreatitis remains the prevention of its occurrence through effective and timely treatment of symptomatic biliary lithiasis.

REFERENCES:

[1] N. Nait Slimane & Al ; Épidémiologie des pancréatites aiguës ; Annales Algériennes de Chirurgie (Juin 2020) T51 – N°1, 22 – 29.

[2] Stephen E. Roberts. The incidence and aetiology of acute pancreatitis across Europe. *Pancreatology*; 10.1016/j.pan.2017.01.005.

[3] Banks PA, Bollen TL, Dervenis C, Gooszen G, Johnson CD, Sarr MG, et al. Classification of acute pancreatitis-2012: revision of the Atlanta classification and definitions by international consensus. *Gut* 2013;62 (1):102-11.

[4] Levy P, Boruchowicz A, Hastier P, Pariente A, Thevenot T, Frossard JL, et al. Diagnostic criteria in predicting a biliary origin of acute pancreatitis in the era of endoscopic ultrasound: multicentre prospective evaluation of 213 patients. *Pancreatology* 2005;5(4- 5):450-6. PubMed PMID: 15985771.

[5] Laurens B, Leroy C, André A, Etienne B, Sergent-Baudson G, Ernst O. Imaging of acute pancreatitis. *J Radiol* 2005 June;86(6 Pt 2):733-747

[6] Dahan P, Andant C, Levy P, Amouyal P, Amouyal G, Dumont M, *et al.* Prospective evaluation of endoscopic ultrasonography and microscopic examination of duodenal bile in the diagnosis of cholecystolithiasis in 45 patients with normal conventional ultrasonography. *Gut* 1996 eb;38(2):277-81. PubMed PMID: 8801211.

[7] Sandrasegaran K, Heller MT, Panda A, Shetty A, Menias CO. MRI in acute pancreatitis. *Abdom Radiol* 2020;45:1232-42. doi: 10.1007/s00261-019-02141-w.

[8] Bollen TL, Singh VK, Maurer R, Repas K, van Es HW, Banks PA, et al. A comparative evaluation of radiologic and clinical scoring systems in the early prediction of severity in acute pancreatitis. *J Am Coll Gastroenterol ACG* 2012;107:612. doi: 10.1038/ajg.2011.438.

[9] Bansal SS, Hodson J, Sutcliffe RS, Marudanayagam R, Muiesan P, Mirza. et al. Performance of the revised Atlanta and determinant-based classifications for severity in acute pancreatitis. *Br J Surg* 2016;103:427-33.

[10] Balthazar E, Freeny P, Van Sonnenberg E. Imaging and intervention in acute pancreatitis. *Radiology* 1994;193:297-306.

[11] Mortele KJ, Wiesner W, Intriere L, Shankar S, Zou KH, Kalantari BN, et al. A modified CT severity index for evaluating acute pancreatitis: improved correlation with patient outcome. *AJR Am J Roentgenol* 2004;183 (5):1261-5.

[12] Khiali R, Ammari S, Nait Slimane N., Draï K, Haicheur EH, Taieb M. Early versus Delayed Cholecystectomy after Mild to Moderate Acute Biliary Pancreatitis: Results of a Comparative Prospective Study. *World J Surg Surgical Res.* 2022; 5: 1362.

[13] van Baal MC, Besselink MG, Bakker OJ, van Santvoort HC, Schaapherder AF, Nieuwenhuijs VB, et al. Timing of cholecystectomy after mild biliary pancreatitis: a systematic review. *Ann Surg* 2012 May;255(5): 860-6. PubMed PMID: 22470079.

[14] Da Costa DW, Bouwense SA, Schepers NJ, Besselink MG, van Santvoort HC, van Brunschot S, et al. Same-admission versus interval cholecystectomy for mild gallstone pancreatitis (PONCHO): A multicentre randomised controlled trial. *Lancet.* 2015;386:1261.

[15] Acute necrotic-hemorrhagic pancreatitis: the Algerian experience. Hammad A et al. Report XIV Maghrebien Medical Congress Tunisia May 1985.

[16] Stratégie de prise en charge des pancréatites aiguës sévères. Thèse de doctorat de sciences médicales; Alger 11February 2008.

[17] Arvanitakis M, Dumonceau JM, Albert J, Badaoui A, Bali MA, Barthet M, et al. Endoscopic management of acute necrotizing pancreatitis: European Society of Gastrointestinal Endoscopy (ESGE) evidence-based multidisciplinary guidelines. *Endoscopy* 2018;50 (5):524-46.

[18] Khashab MA, Tariq A, Tariq U, Kim K, Ponor L, Lennon AM, et al. Delayed and unsuccessful endoscopic retrograde cholangiopancreatography are associated with worse outcomes in patients with acute cholangitis. *Clin Gastroenterol Hepatol* 2012;10(10):1157-61.